

Resting-state fMRI analysis pipeline using FSL and Python: a technical demonstration

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1. Methods

1.1 Data

A resting-state fMRI dataset consisting of 3 healthy control (HC) and 3 schizophrenia (SCZ) patients was used for this analysis.

1.2 DICOM conversion

Raw fMRI DICOM files were converted into NIFTI (.nii.gz) format using `dcm2niix` for downstream preprocessing and analysis.

1.3 Preprocessing

Preprocessing was performed using the FSL FEAT pipeline, including motion correction, temporal filtering, and registration to standard space.

1.4 Group-level ICA analysis

Group-level independent component analysis (ICA) was conducted using FSL MELODIC on the preprocessed fMRI data from all subjects. This approach decomposed the data into spatially independent networks, which were subsequently used for downstream statistical analysis and visualization.

1.5 Network expression analysis and HC vs SCZ comparison

Group ICA spatial maps generated from FSL MELODIC were resampled to each subject's native functional space. Subject-level fMRI data were spatially weighted using the group ICA spatial maps to quantify component-wise signal expression. Mean weighted signal intensity was

extracted for each independent component (IC), generating subject-level IC expression profiles across all networks.

Between-group differences (HC vs SCZ) were calculated for each IC to identify components showing the largest expression differences.

IC spatial maps were visualized using FSLeyes. Network labels were assigned based on spatial overlap with the Yeo 7-network atlas.

All analyses in this section were performed in Python (version 3.9.6).

2. Results

A total of 78 ICs were generated from group ICA analysis. The largest positive HC – SCZ difference was observed in IC21, classified as a dorsal attention-related network. In contrast, IC42 showed the largest negative HC – SCZ difference and was classified as a ventral attention-related network (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Group ICA spatial maps of ICs showing the strongest HC vs SCZ differences. The left panel displays IC21 (dorsal attention network), while the right panel displays IC42 (ventral attention network).